

Context and Considerations for Investigating the Impact of Learning by Doing on Student Equity

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Abstract. Digital learning environments generating large volumes of student data have made it possible to study learning methods and determine effective teaching and learning behaviors. For example, integrating formative practice with text content in a learning by doing approach is highly effective for learning for all learners. When applied in a classroom setting, this method supports increased engagement and outcomes. However, what has yet to be investigated is the impact this method has for the equity gap of at-risk student populations. For universities serving these students, identifying any approach to closing these equity gaps is paramount. In this work, we address the context for this research investigation and discuss important considerations to move forward interpreting the relationship between learning method and student characteristics.

Keywords: Learning by Doing, Artificial Intelligence, Equity.

1 Introduction

Higher education institutions have a responsibility to serve all students equally. As education is a way to overcome historic and systemic inequity, colleges and universities need to increase support for student populations most often at risk, such as racial or ethnic minorities, first generation college students, or transfer students. The University of Central Florida (UCF) is one of the largest public universities in the United States and has large student populations in each of these categories. Therefore, it is necessary to reflect on how teaching and learning methods with educational technology impact these student populations.

One essential advantage of educational technology is the quantity of high quality microlevel data captured by digital learning platforms, and how that data can be used to advance what is known about learning. For example, the student data gathered from courseware—where formative practice is integrated with text content in a learning by doing approach—revealed the learning science principle called the doer effect. Doing practice while reading had about six times the effect on learning than reading alone, and this relationship between doing practice and learning was shown to be causal

[1][2][3]. Research also analyzed the doer effect when controlling for student characteristics such as minority status, gender, age, etc. and found that the doer effect remained [1][4].

Student data from natural learning contexts showed this learning by doing approach was beneficial for all students. This provides confidence that this method should be made available to as many students as possible. Artificial intelligence was applied to generate courseware—and the quantity of formative practice needed for learning by doing—from textbook content in order to deliver this method to more students [5]. The AI generated questions were rigorously evaluated on performance metrics using student data [6], including students and courses at UCF, and student perceptions of these questions were also investigated [7]. The results concluded that AI generated questions performed as well as human-authored questions and students did not perceive a difference, validating their use for learning by doing.

Educational technology and digital learning environments are often designed intentionally to be as ubiquitous as possible [8]. This is true of the AI generated courseware used in this case. The courseware environment needed to be appropriate for use in a great variety of diverse teaching and learning contexts [9]. However, this context-agnostic environment was based on the learning by doing method and intended to elicit the doer effect—known to be beneficial for all students. It is therefore desirable to better understand the impact of this learning by doing environment on these specific at-risk student populations.

In this courseware, no student characteristic data of any kind is collected. While the courseware has predictive models that run adaptive activities and populate instructor data dashboards, these models do not include any student demographics. While there are certainly legal issues involved in this type of information, there are also ethical issues. In this case, there was no compelling reason to include this data in the student modeling. In their review of equity issues in machine learning technologies, Mayfield et al., [10] note that boundaries should be set to protect marginalized populations and, in some cases, machine learning may not be the way to solve some problems. As Baker [11] suggests, the use of demographic data in predictive analytics is controversial and less actionable than learning behavior. This is further supported by research that found learning data to be the most valuable and standalone predictor of student success, over all other readiness assessments and demographic characteristics [12]. Given this, investigating how this learning by doing environment supports specific student groups requires collaboration with the university that holds that information.

Research has also indicated that learning by doing could be beneficial for closing disparities between student outcomes [13]. A meta analysis found that when STEM courses included active learning, students were 1.5 times less likely to fail than courses without it [14]. Theobald et al. [15] conducted a literature review on how active learning impacted Black, Latino, and Indigenous students, along with students from low-income backgrounds, and found that on average, active learning reduced achievement gaps in exam scores and reduced gaps in passing rates. These results provide a reasonable basis for exploring the research question, could AI generated learning by doing in courseware reduce achievement gaps for key at risk student populations at UCF? The goal of this paper is to lay the contextual groundwork for this inquiry and begin a conversation

around the considerations needed to investigate this intersection of learning method and student characteristics.

2 Methods

Between 2020 and 2022, a professor at UCF used SmartStart AI generated courseware based on the course textbook for a Psychology of Sex and Gender course [16]. As the primary learning materials, students were expected to read the text and do the formative practice within the courseware. The instructor applied points to the practice as a homework activity, and engagement and exam scores increased [16]. The data collected from these semesters, along with historic sections without the learning by doing method, are available for analysis.

To investigate the impact of learning by doing on these student populations, multiple data sources need to be combined. First is the raw clickstream data from the courseware which includes all page visits, questions answered, and accuracy data with timestamps attached. This data are also linked to a numeric identifier for students rather than names or emails. Next, student grades would need to be included from the instructor's learning management system gradebook to understand the relationship between doing formative practice and outcomes. Finally, student characteristics would need to be obtained from the university center in order to interpret the engagement and outcome data by these characteristics. Historic grades and student characteristic data would also need to be collected from semesters prior to the use of the courseware to help establish a comparison of outcomes.

3 Discussion

Engaging in this research project would provide a meaningful expansion of what is known about the effects of this learning by doing method on at-risk student populations. Yet there are other complexities to consider when interpreting student characteristics and demographics with learning and outcome data. Each student has a unique personal context—how might that influence the impact of the learning method and environment (designed to be context agnostic)? For example, how do we account for the reality that we cannot be sure if a student's engagement and outcome is at all related to their demographic and not some other contextual factor (e.g., motivation). Serious consideration is required on how to address unanticipated and unknown outside variables in the analysis.

Could this investigation reveal what other research has indicated—that learning behavior is more predictive of success than demographic characteristics? If maximizing all students' engagement with the AI generated practice could mitigate achievement gaps for key student populations, this learning by doing approach could be potentially leveraged at other institutions looking to support equity for all students. While the analysis of these multiple data streams has yet to be accomplished, one key takeaway is that the instructor and their application of learning technology in their courses remains a key for increasing student engagement and outcomes. The intersection of learning by

doing and student characteristics will similarly rely on the successful implementation of pedagogy and technology. As stated by DaVinci (2023): “We see disparities in student success outcomes as an opportunity for faculty and institutional leaders to implement teaching and learning practices and policy changes that will better support marginalized students.”

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